

Pulsations in Cool Eclipsing Binary System V699 Cyg

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Abstract

Aims: We aimed to perform the analysis of the long-term variability and precession of the orbital inclination of the eclipsing binary system V699 Cyg for the first time. **Methods:** We obtained the long-term photometric observation series of the eclipsing binary system V699 Cyg at High-altitude Maidanak Astrophysical Observatory in Uzbekistan and performed the deep analysis of the light curves of V699 Cyg. **Results:** We found that the system changed the orbital inclination. At the same time within eclipse the object periodically changes its brightness with a small amplitude ($\sim 0.037\text{mag}$) within the eclipse. Based on analysis of the all light curves available, we have found that V699 Cyg also exhibit the periodic pulsating oscillations.

1 Introduction

The understanding of physical processes in the binary stars are very important for our knowledge about the Universe. Especially eclipsing binaries provide us with a unique insight into the basic physical parameters of the stars, star clusters, inter-stellar medium, and galaxies. They are also an excellent distance indicators (Zasche, 2008). Eclipsing binaries with pulsating components are essential objects for understanding of stellar structure and evolution. The investigation of oscillations' frequencies known as asteroseismology, helps us to identify the physical processes behind the pulsating nature as well as the stellar interiors. On the other hand, modeling the light and radial velocity curves of an eclipsing binary can precisely determine the physical parameters. This enables one to definitively identify the pulsation modes and compare the results with theoretical models in detail. The study of pulsating stars in eclipsing binaries offers new and strict constraints for stellar theories and helps us to understand the influences of tidal forces and mass transfer among the interacting binaries.

Recent space missions such as CoRoT (Baglin *et al.*, 2006), Kepler/K2 (Borucki *et al.*, 2010) and TESS (Ricker *et al.*, 2014) have dramatically improved our understanding of various phenomena of the stellar variability with a large number of newly detected eclipsing binary systems with pulsation components.

The eclipsing binary V699 Cyg ($V_{max} = 11.^m61$) $\alpha_{2000.0} = 20^h17^m00.^s33$, $\delta_{2000.0} = +39^\circ08'19.57''$ with period $P = 1.5152$ days) was discovered to be a variable by (Whitney, 1952). However photoelectric photometry measurements (Azimov & Zakirov, 1991) have resulted in an amplitude of $\Delta m_B = 0.1$ mag and they found that the primary minimum's amplitude decreased. They were suggesting to interpreted that the massive hot primary filled its Roche lobe. The secondary is a small cool star surrounded by a thick disc. The disc around the system is close to the previous one. Lippky & Marx (1994) (Lippky & Marx, 1994) have analyzed light curves of the V699 Cyg obtained by Whitney (1952), Ro-

mano (1969) (Romano, 1969), and Azimov & Zakirov (1991). Analysing of the light curves, of this eclipsing binary Lippky & Marx (1994) made conclusion. that the binary changed its orbital inclination i

2 Observation & Data Reduction

New photometric observations of V699 Cyg were carried out with the Carl Zeiss-600 (Southern) telescope in August, September and October 2019 at Maidanak Astrophysical Observatory (Uzbekistan). The optical system of the telescope is Cassegrain, the focal length is 7200 mm. The FLI-New 1024 \times 1024 CCD camera was used as the receiver. The read-out noise and gain of the CCD are 8.73 ADUs and 1.24e-, the effective field of view is 6.3×6.3 arcmin, and the pixel scale is 0.372 arcsec per pixel. The filters in the standard Johnson-Cousins multicolour BVR_cI_c photometric system. In total 5528 images in Johnson-Cousins R_c band with 90 second exposure were obtained during these observations. CCD images were processed and analyzed by aperture photometry using the IRAF packages. All images were reduced with master bias, dark, and flat frames by using IRAF (NOAO) package. The photometric processing of the images were done with IRAF/APPHOT utilities. The photometric processing of the images were done with IRAF/APPHOT utilities. The transformation of obtained instrumental magnitudes to the standard international system has been made based on transformation equations and measured extinction coefficients presented in (Artamonov *et al.*, 2010). The coordinates of the target star as well as comparison and check stars used as standards are presented in Table 1.

3 Discussion & Conclusions

We collected all available photometric data on V699 Cyg since its discovery, and the light curves were analyzed with a special focus on the evolution of system's orbital inclination.

We have obtained the total light curve of the V699 Cyg and analyzed measured orbital period. Our analysis of the TESS data has shown a periodic pulsating oscillations in the V699

Figure 1: R-band light curve of V699 Cyg observed on August in 2019 at the Maidanak Astrophysical Observatory.

Figure 2: TESS Sector 55 phase-folded light curves for V699 Cyg with $P = 3.10304$ days.

Figure 3: Phase-binned light curve of VV Ori (filled blue circles) with the best fit from the WD code (red solid line). Bottom: residuals of the fit to the TESS data.

Table 1: Coordinates of the Overcontact Binary V699 Cyg, the Comparison Star (C), and the Check Star (CH).

Stars	$\alpha_{2000.0}$	$\delta_{2000.0}$	R_{mag}
V699 Cyg	$20^h 17^m 00.33^s$	$+39^\circ 08' 19.57''$	11.03
TYC 3151-600-1	$20^h 16^m 56.56^s$	$+38^\circ 57' 17.09''$	10.95
TYC 3151-480-1	$20^h 17^m 13.95^s$	$+39^\circ 06' 18.42''$	10.23

Cyg light curves too. The same pulsation variations were found by Southworth et al. (2021) in the light curve of eclipsing binary star VV Ori based on analysis of its TESS data. The comparison and the difference between the TESS light curves and the model generated by the WD-code (Southworth et al., 2021) is represented in Figure 3. All these mean that V699 Cyg could also be a candidate for pulsating eclipsing binary system. Based on a thorough analysis of the photometric behavior of the eclipsing binary system V699 Cyg, it can be argued with a high degree of probability that, along with the features of an eclipsing binary system, V699 Cyg clearly demonstrates also a pulsating activity, the discovering of which is important both for understanding of the complex physical processes occurring in the stellar system, and inside these stars.

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